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Characterization of photoelastic materials by Mach-Zehnder interferometry: Application to trigonal calcium galogermanate (CGG) crystals

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ABSTRACT

We explore piezooptic and photoelastic properties of $\text{Ca}_3\text{Ga}_2\text{Ge}_4\text{O}_{14}$ (CGG) crystals. A Mach-Zehnder interferometry technique is utilized to determine a complete set of the piezooptic tensor constants π_{im} , with particular attention to the measurement accuracy, reliability, and uncertainty resolution in the piezooptic measurements. For these reasons, independent piezooptic constants or their combinations were determined by performing interferometric measurements for different geometries of piezooptic coupling using samples of both principal (direct) and non-principal ($X/45^\circ$) crystallographic cuts. Basing on the results of piezooptic measurements, a complete set of photoelastic tensor constants p_{im} and the acousto-optic performance (figure of merit M_2) of CGG crystals were evaluated. The obtained piezooptic, photoelastic, and acousto-optic characteristics of CGG crystals are compared with those of other crystals of the langasite group, langasite and CTGS ($\text{Ca}_3\text{TaGa}_3\text{Si}_2\text{O}_{14}$). A comparative analysis reveals a correlation between the values of the piezooptic or photoelastic constants and the lattice parameters for this group of crystals. High optical quality and optical transparency in the UV region of the spectrum up to 260 nm together with extremely high mechanical resistance to uniaxial compression ($\leq 2000 \text{ kg/cm}^2$) opens up the possibility for specific application of CGG crystal as an optical material for piezooptic sensors of high uniaxial compression. The presented piezooptic interference technique along with methodological and metrological approaches paves the way for accurate and unambiguous characterization of photoelastic crystal materials of trigonal symmetry.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Calcium galogermanate crystals $\text{Ca}_3\text{Ga}_2\text{Ge}_4\text{O}_{14}$ (CGG) belong to $\text{A}_3\text{BC}_3\text{D}_2\text{O}_{14}$ group of inorganic crystalline materials with trigonal symmetry, i.e., the family of langasite (LGS) crystals^{1,2} intensively studied in recent years due to their high piezoelectric, photoelastic, acousto-optic, and nonlinear optical efficiency making them promising for acousto-electronic and optoelectronic applications.^{3–18} Langasite $\text{La}_3\text{Ga}_5\text{SiO}_{14}$ was one of the first grown crystals with such a structure whereas extensive studies of other crystals of this group allow us to draw relevant conclusions about the impact of cationic substitution both on the crystal structure and related physical properties.^{1,3–5} By changing the chemical composition, these studies are aimed at improving

the physical characteristics of crystalline materials for relevant applications.^{1,6–8} For example, the cationic substitution of Ca by Sr in CGG crystals approximately doubles the values of the piezoelectric constants d_{11} and d_{14} .⁹ It should be noted that crystals of this group, such as, e.g., LGS, CTGS, CNGS, etc., do not reveal phase transformations up to melting temperatures of 1300–1500 °C.¹⁰ They demonstrate high temperature stability of physical characteristics, in particular, elastic constants,^{10–12} low attenuation of acoustic waves (several times smaller than that of crystalline quartz⁹), large piezoelectric effect and electromechanical coupling,^{9,13,14} as well as a high threshold of optical damage ($\sim 1 \text{ GW/cm}^2$), which is an order of magnitude higher than in the known electro- and acousto-optic lithium niobate crystal.¹⁴ All this makes the crystals of the langasite group unique and suitable

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for wide range of applications in acousto- and optoelectronic devices.^{14–18}

Optical characterization of LGS type crystals has been concentrated basically on luminescent, refractive, spectroscopic,^{9,19,20} photoelastic, and acousto-optic^{21–23} properties in recent years. Derived in these studies, photoelastic and acousto-optic characteristics evidently indicate that LGS and CTGS crystals represent efficient acousto-optic materials suitable for light modulation in the ultraviolet spectral region. It should be noted that piezooptical and photoelastic characteristics were also studied for CGG crystals.²⁴ However, in this work only, the principal piezooptical constants (POCs) π_{im} and photoelastic constants (PECs) p_{ik} ($i, m, k = 1, 2, 3$) have been explored. Challenging, in particular, for determining POCs π_{14} , π_{41} , π_{44} and PECs p_{14} , p_{41} , p_{44} were actually not evaluated, since the errors in determining these constants turned out to be larger than their values. Therefore, in this work, using the interferometric method, we provide a complete characterization of POCs and PECs tensors for CGG crystal, namely, present the values of both principal and non-principal components. Much attention is paid to accuracy, reliability, and uncertainty resolution in the piezooptical measurements. For these reasons, independent piezooptical constants or their combinations were determined by performing interferometric measurements for different geometries of piezooptical coupling using samples of both principal (direct) and non-principal ($X/45^\circ$) crystallographic cuts. Obtained results are compared with similar studies for CTGS and LGS crystals,^{21,25} whereas presented methodological and metrological approaches pave the way for accurate and unambiguous characterization of photoelastic crystal materials of trigonal symmetry.

II. PIEZOOPTICAL INTERFEROMETRIC TECHNIQUE AND METHOD DESCRIPTION

CGG belongs to the crystals of the langasite family with a disordered structure² described by the point group symmetry 32 (space group P321).⁹ Relevant tensor matrices of piezooptical (π_{im}) and photoelastic (p_{ik}) constants contain 18 nonzero components, wherein 8 are independent,²⁶

$$[\pi_{im}] = \begin{pmatrix} \pi_{11} & \pi_{12} & \pi_{13} & \pi_{14} & 0 & 0 \\ \pi_{12} & \pi_{11} & \pi_{13} & -\pi_{14} & 0 & 0 \\ \pi_{31} & \pi_{31} & \pi_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \pi_{41} & -\pi_{41} & 0 & \pi_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \pi_{44} & 2\pi_{41} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \pi_{14} & \pi_{66} \end{pmatrix}; \quad (1)$$

$$[p_{ik}] = \begin{pmatrix} p_{11} & p_{12} & p_{13} & p_{14} & 0 & 0 \\ p_{12} & p_{11} & p_{13} & -p_{14} & 0 & 0 \\ p_{31} & p_{31} & p_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ p_{41} & -p_{41} & 0 & p_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & p_{44} & p_{41} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & p_{14} & p_{66} \end{pmatrix};$$

$$\pi_{66} = \pi_{11} - \pi_{12}; \text{ and } p_{66} = (p_{11} - p_{12})/2.$$

Five principal independent POCs π_{11} , π_{12} , π_{13} , π_{31} , and π_{33} are determined by the piezooptical interferometric technique [Fig. 1(a)] on a rectangular sample of principal crystallographic cuts, i.e., the sample with faces being perpendicular to the crystallographic axes

FIG. 1. (a) Experimental setup for piezooptical measurements based on Mach-Zehnder interferometer technique. M —mirrors, P —polarizers, and PD —photodiode. Sample S is subjected to uniaxial compression σ . (b) Rectangular sample of principal (direct) crystallographic cut: the faces are perpendicular to the principal crystallographic axes ($X=1$, $Y=2$, and $Z=3$). (c) Non-principal crystallographic $X/45^\circ$ -cut.

X , Y , and Z , see Fig. 1(b). Non-principal POCs π_{14} , π_{41} , and π_{44} , on the other hand, are determined on the $X/45^\circ$ -cut sample sketched in Fig. 1(c). Here, the directions 1, 2, and 3 correspond to the X , Y , and Z axes of the optical indicatrix. Direction 4 and perpendicular to it direction $\bar{4}$ correspond to the bisector between the axes Y and Z . It is remarkable that the $X/45^\circ$ -cut sample appears to be suitable for determining the principal POC π_{11} , as well as sums of principal POCs, e.g., $\pi_{21} + \pi_{31}$, $\pi_{12} + \pi_{13}$, and several others. Accordingly, by comparing these POC sums with the sums of the relevant π_{im} constants determined on a sample of principal crystallographic cut, we can confirm the validity of the derived POC values and/or verify the piezooptical identity and homogeneity of samples being cut from different parts of the same crystal boule or various ones.

To determine the POC π_{im} by the interferometric method, one should find the change in the optical path $\delta\Delta_k$ of the beam passing through the sample under the action of the mechanical stress σ_m on the crystal,²⁷

$$\delta\Delta_k = -\frac{1}{2}\pi_{im}\sigma_m d_k n_i^3 + S_{km}\sigma_m d_k (n_i - 1), \quad (2)$$

where n_i is the refractive index of the crystal, d_k is the thickness of the sample in the direction of propagation of the interferometer beam, S_{km} is the elastic compliance constant, and indices k, i , and

m denote the directions of light propagation, the polarization, and the direction of uniaxial stress σ_m , respectively. This expression is valid for a single-pass interferometer (e.g., Mach-Zehnder) when the interferometer beam passes through the sample once. The piezooptic interferometric setup used in our studies is sketched in Fig. 1(a).

For the well-known method of half-wave stresses, the change in the optical path $\delta\Delta_k$ equals $\lambda/2$ (λ is the light wavelength), and $\sigma_m = \sigma_{im}$ is the half-wave mechanical stress. Accordingly, expression (2) is reduced to a simple form

$$\pi_{im} = -\frac{\lambda}{n_i^3 \sigma_{im} d_k} + 2S_{km} \frac{(n_i - 1)}{n_i^3} = -\frac{\lambda}{n_i^3 \sigma_{im}^o} + 2S_{km} \frac{(n_i - 1)}{n_i^3}, \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma_{im}^o = \sigma_{im} \cdot d_k$ is the path length normalized half-wave stress (hereafter NHW-stress), which is characteristic of the material, in contrast to the half-wave stress σ_{im} , which is characteristic of the sample since it depends on its dimensions. By substituting the values of the indices k , i , and m into (3) that correspond to the specific geometry of piezooptic interaction (directions of uniaxial compression, light propagation, and polarization, hereafter *piezooptic geometry*) used in piezooptic measurements, it is easy to derive expressions for determination of the principal POCs π_{im} , for details see, e.g., Ref. 21. On the other hand, relations for non-principal POCs or sums of main POCs, such as, e.g., $\pi_{12} + \pi_{13}$, which should be determined by performing piezooptic measurements on the $X/45^\circ$ -cut sample [Fig. 1(c)], appear to be more complicated. For example, POC π_{44} is defined using the following relation:^{21,27}

$$\pi_{22} + \pi_{23} + \pi_{32} + \pi_{33} + 2\pi_{44} = -\frac{2\lambda}{n_4^3} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_{44}^o} + \frac{1}{\sigma_{44}^o} \right) + 2(S_{11} + 2S_{13} + S_{33} - S_{44}) \frac{n_4 - 1}{n_4^3}, \quad (4)$$

where the NHW-stress values σ_{44}^o and σ_{44}^o are determined by using the two different sample geometries in the piezooptic measurements: $m = i = 4, k = \bar{4}$ and $m = i = \bar{4}, k = 4$, correspondingly. We emphasize that POCs π_{22} , π_{23} , and π_{32} in Eq. (4) can be replaced by π_{11} , π_{13} , and π_{31} , respectively, which follows from specific relations between the values of the POCs matrix, see Eq. (1). All other necessary relations have been derived in Refs. 21 and 27, which, in particular, will be applied to determine the non-principal POCs or sums of type $\pi_{12} + \pi_{13}$ using the $X/45^\circ$ -cut sample in the piezooptic measurements. In addition, we provide below the expressions for determining the elastic constant S_{14} by applying the piezooptic technique. Relevant relations are necessary to verify the sign of the coefficient S_{14} . Using the equations derived in Ref. 27 for the $X/45^\circ$ -cut sample, the relations for POC π_{11} read as

$$\pi_{11} = -\frac{\lambda}{n_1^3 \sigma_{11}^o |_{k=4}} + (S_{12} + S_{13} + S_{14}) \frac{n_1 - 1}{n_1^3}, \quad (5)$$

for piezooptic geometry $k = 4, m = i = 1$, and

$$\pi_{11} = -\frac{\lambda}{n_1^3 \sigma_{11}^o |_{k=\bar{4}}} + (S_{12} + S_{13} - S_{14}) \frac{n_1 - 1}{n_1^3}, \quad (6)$$

for piezooptic geometry $k = \bar{4}, m = i = 1$.

It should be emphasized here that in piezooptic measurements coherent light propagates along the different (orthogonal) crystallo-physical directions, $k = 4$ and $k = \bar{4}$ [Fig. 1(c)], thereby relevant Eqs. (5) and (6) differ only by the sign at the elastic compliance S_{14} . Therefore, by adding these equations, one obtains π_{11} -value:

$$\pi_{11} = -\frac{\lambda}{2n_1^3} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_{11}^o |_{k=4}} + \frac{1}{\sigma_{11}^o |_{k=\bar{4}}} \right) + (S_{12} + S_{13}) \frac{n_1 - 1}{n_1^3}, \quad (7)$$

whereas their difference gives S_{14} -value:

$$S_{14} = \frac{\lambda}{2(n_1 - 1)} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_{11}^o |_{k=4}} - \frac{1}{\sigma_{11}^o |_{k=\bar{4}}} \right). \quad (8)$$

We will use these expressions when analyzing the results of piezooptic measurements obtained on the $X/45^\circ$ -cut sample.

III. PIEZOOPTIC INTERFEROMETRIC MEASUREMENTS AND THEIR ANALYSIS

The POCs π_{im} were determined by the interferometric method in a static mode using the Mach-Zehnder interferometer technique,²⁸ see Fig. 1(a). Samples in the form of cubes with dimensions $\sim 7 \times 7 \times 7 \text{ mm}^3$ were studied. They were prepared providing high parallelism of the optical faces: deviations of the thickness of the samples over the entire area of such faces did not exceed $2 \mu\text{m}$. In this case, the error in determining the POC π_{im} caused by the microwedge shape of the optical faces of the samples is negligible, for relevant analysis see Refs. 25 and 29. It is noteworthy that for the crystals characterized by symmetry classes 32, 3m, and m there is an ambiguity in the definition of the POC π_{14} and π_{41} , both in terms of sign and absolute value.^{21,25} Therefore, directions 4 and $\bar{4}$ [Fig. 1(c)] should be clearly fixed. It is sufficient for this to fix the positive direction for the X axis [$X \parallel 1$, Fig. 1(c)]. Fortunately, the large piezoelectricity in CGG crystals along the X axis ($d_{11} \sim 5 \text{ pK/N}^9$) makes it easy to distinguish positively and negatively charged faces induced piezoelectrically. Accordingly, the positive direction of the X axis is taken in the direction perpendicular to the positively charged face, which arises under the action of positive (tensile) stress applied along this direction. The values of elastic compliance tensor S_{km} ⁹ and inverse to it tensor of elastic constants C_{mk} used, in particular, for determination of POCs π_{im} and PECs p_{im} of CGG crystals, respectively, are given in Table I. The magnitudes of refractive indices $n_1 = n_o = 1.808$ and $n_3 = n_e = 1.824$ ($T = 20^\circ\text{C}$, $\lambda = 632.8 \text{ nm}$), necessary for the calculation of the principal POCs, are also taken from Ref. 9. The refractive indices along the diagonal directions 4 and $\bar{4}$ ($n_4 = n_{\bar{4}} = 1.816$), are found using the known relation $n_4 = n_{\bar{4}} = \sqrt{2}/\sqrt{a_2^2 + a_3^2}$, where $a_i = 1/n_i^2$ ($i = 2, 3$) are the optical polarization constants.

TABLE I. Elastic compliances S_{km} (in $10^{-12} \text{ m}^2/\text{N}$) and elastic constants C_{mk} (in 10^{10} N/m^2) of CGG crystals (Ref. 9).

S_{11}	10.25	C_{11}	15.55
S_{12}	-5.19	C_{12}	8.67
S_{13}	-1.54	C_{13}	7.29
S_{33}	5.11	C_{33}	23.96
S_{44}	23.33	C_{44}	4.55
S_{14}	-3.23 (+3.33 ^a)	C_{14}	0.95 (-0.95 ^a)
S_{66}	30.87	C_{66}	3.44

^aValues determined in the present work.

The values of the NHW-stress σ_{im}^o and POCs π_{im} of CGG crystals obtained from piezooptic interferometric measurements are listed in Table II. The errors of the calculated POCs π_{im} presented here are defined by the accuracy of NHW-stress measurements

TABLE II. The values of the NHW-stress σ_{im}^o and POCs π_{im} (1 Br = $10^{-12} \text{ m}^2/\text{N}$) of CGG crystals obtained by the results of piezooptic interferometric measurements ($\lambda = 632.8 \text{ nm}$, $T = 20^\circ \text{C}$).

No.	Piezooptic geometry			σ_{im}^o (kg/cm)	π_{im} (Br)
	m	k	i		
Principal crystallographic cut sample [Fig. 1(b)]					
1	1	2	1	$\sigma_{11}^o = 98$	$\pi_{11} = -0.30 \pm 0.13$
2			3	$\sigma_{31}^o = 48.5$	$\pi_{31} = 0.78 \pm 0.23$
3	1	3	1	$\sigma_{11}^o = 750$	$\pi_{11} = -0.28 \pm 0.03$
4			2	$\sigma_{21}^o = 320$	$\pi_{21} = -0.08 \pm 0.04$
5	2	1	2	$\sigma_{22}^o = 100$	$\pi_{22} = -0.33 \pm 0.13$
6			3	$\sigma_{32}^o = 49.5$	$\pi_{32} = 0.74 \pm 0.23$
7	2	3	2	$\sigma_{22}^o = 700$	$\pi_{22} = -0.26 \pm 0.03$
8			1	$\sigma_{12}^o = 340$	$\pi_{12} = -0.10 \pm 0.04$
9	3	1	3	$\sigma_{33}^o = -275^a$	$\pi_{33} = -0.81 \pm 0.04$
10			2	$\sigma_{23}^o = 155$	$\pi_{23} = 0.28 \pm 0.07$
11	3	2	3	$\sigma_{33}^o = -290^a$	$\pi_{33} = -0.79 \pm 0.04$
12			1	$\sigma_{13}^o = 151$	$\pi_{13} = 0.30 \pm 0.08$
Non-principal $X/45^\circ$ -cut sample [Fig. 1(c)]					
13	1	4	1	$\sigma_{11}^o = 600$	$\pi_{11} = -0.28 \pm 0.11$
14			$\bar{4}$	$\sigma_{41}^o = 180$	$\pi_{41} = 0.26 \pm 0.11$
15	1	$\bar{4}$	1	$\sigma_{11}^o = 100$	$\pi_{11} = -0.28 \pm 0.11$
16			4	$\sigma_{41}^o = 54$	$\pi_{21} + \pi_{31} = 0.76 \pm 0.22$
17	4	1	2	$\sigma_{24}^o = 400$	$\pi_{24} = -0.30 \pm 0.15$
18	$\bar{4}$	1	2	$\sigma_{24}^o = 75$	$\pi_{22} + \pi_{23} = -0.11 \pm 0.17^b$
19	4	$\bar{4}$	1	$\sigma_{14}^o = 105$	$\pi_{14} = 0.23 \pm 0.13$
20			4	$\sigma_{44}^o = 310$	$\pi_{44} = -0.53 \pm 0.23$
21	$\bar{4}$	4	1	$\sigma_{14}^o = 135$	$\pi_{12} + \pi_{13} = 0.34 \pm 0.22$
22			$\bar{4}$	$\sigma_{44}^o = 170$	$\pi_{24} + 2\pi_{42} = -0.60 \pm 0.14$

^aNegative σ_{33}^o -value (rows 9 and 11) indicates on a decrease in the optical path under the uniaxial compression which is considered during the calculations.

^bDerived value of the POCs sum, $\pi_{22} + \pi_{23}$ (row 18), appears within the error of its determination.

with a relative error of 10%, typical for the interferometric techniques, and the accuracy of S_{km} -values provided in Ref. 9, for which the relative error is assumed to be equal 5%. It should be noted here that for a number of crystals, including those of the LGS group, the deviations of the values of elastic constants given by various authors indeed do not exceed 5% (see, for example, Refs. 30 and 31), which justifies the choice of such an error value. Considering then Eq. (3), the errors of the POCs π_{im} were calculated as the root-mean-square value of the sum of the errors of its first and second terms. In the case of more complex relations, for example, Eq. (4), which include the sums of the coefficients π_{im} and S_{km} , the root-mean-square errors of such sums were determined. Other approaches concerning the error analysis may be found in Refs. 25 and 32.

In a number of cases, Table II presents the values of the same POCs π_{im} obtained using different piezooptic geometries. Based on these data, Table III provides their final average magnitudes for CGG crystals. The POC values for CTGS and LGS crystals reported in previous studies^{21,25} are also listed here for comparison. Below we provide a brief analysis of the data presented in Tables II and III.

Analyzing, in particular, the data given in Table II and considering that $\pi_{22} = \pi_{11}$ [Eq. (1)], we see that the POC π_{11} was found using six different piezooptic geometries in the interferometric measurements (see lines 1, 3, 5, 7, 13, and 15), wherein in two cases, the $X/45^\circ$ -cut sample has been explored. However, the value of π_{11} presented in Table III represents the average of the values given in lines 3 and 7 (Table II), since the errors for the corresponding piezooptic geometries are very small in these cases, $\delta\pi_{11} = \delta\pi_{22} = 0.03 \text{ Br}$. Other principal POCs π_{im} ($i, m = 1, 2, 3$), namely, $\pi_{12} = \pi_{21}$, $\pi_{13} = \pi_{23}$, $\pi_{31} = \pi_{32}$ and π_{33} , as well as non-principal POCs $\pi_{14} = -\pi_{24}$, $\pi_{41} = -\pi_{42}$ and π_{44} were found using in each case two different piezooptic geometries in the interferometric measurements, thus Table III lists their average values. Remarkably, all particular POCs π_{im} , determined from different piezooptic geometries, are characterized by the same values with the errors of their determination, which confirms the reliability of the values presented here. A more comprehensive analysis compares the sums of POCs determined on the $X/45^\circ$ -cut sample (Table II, rows 16, 18, and 21) with the relevant sums composed of the same principal POCs but determined independently in other suitable piezooptic geometries, in particular, by measuring the principal cut samples. For example, the sum of POCs $\pi_{21} + \pi_{31} = 0.76 \pm 0.22 \text{ Br}$ directly determined on the $X/45^\circ$ -cut sample (Table II, row 16) agrees within the experimental error with the sum of POCs π_{31} (Table II, row 2) and π_{21} (Table II, row 4) obtained directly on the principal cut sample, relevant sum equals $0.70 \pm 0.23 \text{ Br}$. Accordingly, we can conclude about the good convergence of these results, which independently confirms, on the one hand, the reliability of the derived principal POCs values π_{im} , and on the other hand, the reliability of the results obtained in the interferometric measurements of non-principal $X/45^\circ$ -cut samples.

It is noteworthy that piezooptic measurements provide the possibility for determination of the elastic compliance S_{14} by the piezooptic method. If we substitute into Eq. (8), the values of the NHW-stress determined for different directions of light propagation, i.e., $\sigma_{11}^o |_{k=4}$ (Table II, row 13) and $\sigma_{11}^o |_{k=\bar{4}}$ (Table II, row 15),

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TABLE III. Complete sets of independent POCs π_{im} and PECs p_{ik} of CGG, CTGS, and LGS crystals ($\lambda = 632.8$ nm, $T = 20$ °C).

π_{im} (Br)	π_{11}	π_{12}	π_{13}	π_{31}	π_{33}	π_{14}	π_{41}	π_{44}
CGG	-0.27	-0.09	0.29	0.76	-0.80	0.27	0.26	-0.52
This work	± 0.03	± 0.04	± 0.075	± 0.23	± 0.04	± 0.14	± 0.11	± 0.23
CTGS	-0.19	0.22	0.53	1.40	-1.20	0.72	0.32	-0.8
21	± 0.06	± 0.09	± 0.12	± 0.19	± 0.09	± 0.11	± 0.11	± 0.40
LGS	-0.17	0.10	0.30	0.70	-1.25	0.32	0.33	0.35
21 and 25	± 0.07	± 0.07	± 0.08	± 0.19	± 0.08	± 0.15	± 0.12	± 0.16
p_{im}	p_{11}	p_{12}	p_{13}	p_{31}	p_{33}	p_{14}	p_{41}	p_{44}
CGG	-0.033	-0.015	0.038	0.126	-0.081	0.014	0.023	-0.029
This work	± 0.008	± 0.009	± 0.017	± 0.042	± 0.028	± 0.006	± 0.020	± 0.011
CTGS	0.008 ^a	0.044	0.096	0.165	-0.088	0.029	0.029	-0.033
21	± 0.010	± 0.013	± 0.022	± 0.031	± 0.031	± 0.005	± 0.015	± 0.017
LGS	0.014 ^a	0.027	0.071	0.078	-0.181	0.013	0.033	0.028
21	± 0.016	± 0.017	± 0.021	± 0.047	± 0.049	± 0.009	± 0.027	± 0.009

^aDerived value is smaller than the relevant experimental error.

one obtains $S_{14} = (+3.33 \pm 0.40) \times 10^{-12}$ m²/N. This value will agree with the magnitude of the S_{14} constant reported in Ref. 9 (Table I) but is opposite in sign. One should be emphasized here that the sign of S_{14} turns out to be crucial for a correct determination of π_{24} and π_{41} POCs since the S_{14} constant directly enters into the expressions defining these POCs,^{21,27}

$$\pi_{24} = -\frac{\lambda}{n_1^3} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_{24}^o} - \frac{1}{\sigma_{24}^o} \right) + 2S_{14} \frac{n_1 - 1}{n_1^3}, \quad (9)$$

$$\pi_{41} = -\frac{\lambda}{2n_4^3} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_{41}^o} - \frac{1}{\sigma_{41}^o} \right) - S_{14} \frac{n_4 - 1}{n_4^3}. \quad (10)$$

For example, if we subsequently substitute into Eq. (9), the values of the NHW-stress, σ_{24}^o and σ_{24}^o (Table II, rows 17 and 18), and the value of S_{14} taken with different signs, i.e., (+) and (-), one get considerably different results for POC π_{14} , likewise symmetry related POC π_{24} ($\pi_{24} = -\pi_{14}$), namely, 0.30 ± 0.15 Br and about seven times larger value, 2.07 ± 0.15 Br, respectively. Comparing these magnitudes with the π_{14} -value determined in piezooptic geometry independent of the S_{14} constant^{21,27} ($\pi_{14} = 0.23 \pm 0.13$ Br, see Table II, row 19), one may conclude about a positive sign of the S_{14} constant. A similar conclusion can be drawn considering the symmetry related POCs π_{41} and π_{42} ($\pi_{41} = -\pi_{42}$) defined in two different piezooptic geometries (Table II, rows 14 and 22). Accordingly, for an unambiguous and correct determination of the POCs π_{14} or π_{41} , it is necessary to fix properly the crystallophysical coordinate system. In this work, we explicitly refer to a right-hand coordinate system, for which the positive direction of the X axis is determined based on the piezoelectric effect, as discussed above. It should be noted that for the selected right-hand coordinate system, the sign of the elastic constant C_{14} , similarly as in the case of the S_{14} component, must be changed to the opposite, which is indicated in Table I. This becomes evident by applying the

inverse transformation to the S_{km} -matrix, which gives $C_{14} = -S_{14}/(S_{11}S_{44} - S_{12}S_{44} - 2S_{14}^2)$. Therefore, when calculating PECs p_{11} , p_{12} , p_{14} , p_{41} , and p_{44} , the correct result is provided only if the C_{14} constant is taken with a (-) sign. Calculations of PECs are based on the well-known tensor relation,²⁶

$$p_{ik} = \pi_{im} C_{mk}, \quad (11)$$

as well as expressions for estimating errors derived in Refs. 21 and 27. The results of the corresponding calculations, which are summarized in Table III, can be characterized as follows:

- (i) All POCs of the CGG crystal are relatively small (≤ 1 Br). For comparison, the POCs π_{31} and π_{33} of the CTGS crystal belonging to the same group are characterized by values slightly larger than 1 Br. The LGS crystal has only one such constant (π_{33}), wherein POCs π_{31} and π_{33} for all three crystals demonstrate the largest values.
- (ii) PEC p_{31} reveals the largest value for CGG and CTGS crystals, whereas, for LGS, this is the p_{33} constant, which is also ~ 2 times larger than p_{33} of CGG and CTGS. In general, PECs p_{31} and p_{33} , likewise as POCs π_{31} and π_{33} , are characterized by the largest magnitudes for all these crystals. All other PECs are significantly (from 2.5 to 20 times) smaller. Relevant PEC values should be considered as reliable because they have been calculated using reliable magnitudes of POCs which, similar as in Refs. 21 and 25, have been determined independently using different piezooptic geometries and which passed appropriate convergence tests. It must be admitted that there are also other methods for determining the PECs, such as, e.g., Dixon-Cohen methods,^{33,34} Brillouin scattering,^{35,36} techniques used by Pettersen³⁷ or Narasimhamurti.²⁶ However, these methods either fail to determine the sign of PECs or allow only combinations of PECs to be found, while relatively low accuracy results in a wide spread of PEC values reported by different authors.

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Therefore, the interferometric technique along with the described above methodology should be classified as the most reliable approach for the characterization of piezooptic and photoelastic properties in crystalline materials.

- (iii) The obtained results evidently suggest a certain correlation between the POCs or PECs values and the lattice parameters in the langasite group crystals. In particular, larger effects are observed in CTGS and LGS crystals, which are characterized by a larger unit cell volume, $V = 283.80 \text{ \AA}^3$ ³⁸ and $V = 294.28 \text{ \AA}^3$ ³⁹, respectively, compared with, e.g., CGG crystals ($V = 279.96 \text{ \AA}^3$ ⁴⁰). A certain correlation also exists between POCs or PECs values and the ratio of cell parameters c/a . In particular, the longitudinal effects related to the constants π_{33} and p_{33} (Table III) prevail in LGS crystals, which are characterized by a larger value of $c/a = 0.6233$,⁶ whereas for CTGS and CGG crystals with smaller ratio c/a (0.6148³⁸ and 0.6158,⁴⁰ respectively), the transverse effects described by the constants π_{31} and p_{31} prevail (Table III).
- (iv) Available data allow us to estimate an acousto-optic efficiency of CGG crystals. The acousto-optic figure of merit M_2 can be calculated using the well-known expression $M_2 = n_i^6 p_{ik}^2 / \rho V_k^3$, where $\rho = 4.589 \times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$ is the density of the CGG crystal, V_k is the velocity of the acoustic wave, and n_i is the refractive index.^{33,34,41} For the geometry of the acousto-optical coupling associated with the largest PEC $p_{31} = 0.126$ (Table III), refractive index $n_3 = 1.824$ and ultrasonic velocity $V_1 = 5850 \text{ m/s}$ ⁹ of the longitudinal acoustic wave propagating along the X axis one obtains $M_2 = 0.64 \times 10^{-15} \text{ s}^3/\text{kg}$. This value is ~ 2 times larger compared to the strontium borate (SrB_4O_7) crystal, widely applied for acousto-optical light modulation in the ultraviolet (UV) spectral range,²⁹ but is somewhat smaller compared to LGS or CTGS crystals.²¹ Ultimately, higher acousto-optical efficiency CGG may be reached via optimization of the geometry of acousto-optical coupling. Relevant approaches^{22,23,32,42,45} consider indicative M_2 -surfaces which characterize the spatial anisotropy of the acousto-optic efficiency. It is noteworthy that actual work provides a full set of photoelastic tensor constants p_{im} necessary for calculating the indicative surfaces. However, relevant analysis appears beyond the scope of the current study and will be considered elsewhere.
- (v) One should note that CGG crystals, in addition to their high optical quality, resistance to the aggressiveness of external environment, and transparency in the deep UV region of the spectrum down to 260 nm⁹ have in accordance in our data extremely high mechanical resistance against the uniaxial compression, up to 2000 kg/cm². This opens up the possibility for their specific application as mechanically high resistance optical materials for piezooptic sensors of uniaxial compression.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The present study explores piezooptic and photoelastic properties of $\text{Ca}_3\text{Ga}_2\text{Ge}_4\text{O}_{14}$ (CGG) crystals. A Mach-Zehnder interferometer is utilized to measure a full set of tensor piezooptic constants (POCs) π_{im} for these crystals, with particular attention paid to the measurement accuracy, reliability, and uncertainty

resolution in the interferometric piezooptic measurements. For these reasons, independent POCs or their combination have been determined by performing piezooptic measurements for various geometries of piezooptic coupling using the samples of principal (direct) and non-principal ($X/45^\circ$) crystallographic cuts. In particular, the POC π_{11} was determined independently for six different piezooptic geometries, two of which are associated with the samples of non-principal $X/45^\circ$ -cut. The values of specific POCs obtained independently for different piezooptic geometries coincide with the experimental errors of their determination. Reliability of the interferometric piezooptic measurements is also proved by the convergence of POCs sums, such as, e.g., $\pi_{21} + \pi_{31}$, $\pi_{12} + \pi_{13}$, etc., measured directly on $X/45^\circ$ -cut sample, with sums of relevant POCs measured independently on the rectangular samples of principal crystallographic cuts.

Based on the results of piezooptic interferometric measurements and elastic constants reported in Ref. 9, we have determined a complete set of photoelastic tensor constants and evaluated the acousto-optic figure of merit M_2 of CGG crystals. The obtained photoelastic and acousto-optic characteristics are compared with those of other crystals of the langasite group—LGS and CTGS. For the geometry of the acousto-optic coupling associated with the largest PEC $p_{31} = 0.126$, we obtain $M_2 = 0.64 \times 10^{-15} \text{ s}^3/\text{kg}$. This value is approximately twice larger compared to SrB_4O_7 crystals, i.e., a widely used acousto-optic material in the UV range, and only slightly smaller compared to LGS or CTGS crystals. Among the obvious advantages of CGG crystals are high optical quality, resistance to the aggressiveness of the external environment, and transparency in the UV region of the spectrum up to 260 nm, which, along with extremely high mechanical resistance to uniaxial compression ($\leq 2000 \text{ kg/cm}^2$), opens up the possibility of their specific application as optical materials for piezooptic sensors of high uniaxial compression. The presented piezooptic interference technique, on the other hand, along with provided methodological and metrological approaches pave the way for accurate and unambiguous characterization of photoelastic crystal materials of trigonal symmetry.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

B. H. Mytsyk: Conceptualization (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – original draft (equal).

N. M. Demyanyshyn: Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal). **A. S. Andrushchak:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Methodology (equal). **Yu. Ya. Maksishko:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal). **Z. O. Kohut:** Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Visualization (equal). **A. V. Kityk:** Formal analysis (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available within the article.

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